

The lost archaic paintings of Sivré IV (Ennedi, Chad)

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Abstract: The Sivré hill in the Ennedi, well-known for the two “Martians” discovered by Gérard Bailloud in 1957, hosts in its shelters some paintings attributable to the pre-pastoral period, not surveyed at the time of the first reporting but only mentioned. In particular, the overlooked weathered paintings present in two secluded shelters southwest of Sivré IV, show that the site is richer of a diverse pre-pastoral art than it was possible to imagine from the previously published descriptions. The superimposition relations among these ancient paintings are consistent with the relative regional chronology proposed for the oldest painting styles in the Ennedi.

Keywords: rock art, pictographs, Sivré, Ennedi, Chad, Sahara.

Figure 1. Location map of the Sivré painted sites. The numbering of the decorated shelters is in roman numerals, from one to four, clockwise along the terrace, as initially established by Bailloud (1997). The sites labelled with a numbered “P” host art of the Recent Cattle, Final Cattle and Camel periods. The satellite image in the background is from Digital Globe - (Westminster, CO, USA) - Google Earth (Google, Inc., Mountain View, CA, USA).

1. Introduction

Sivré is a small tabular hill made of Cambrian fluvial sandstones (MEH 2015), located in the southwestern sector of the Ennedi Highland in Chad (Fig. 1). It covers an area of less than 1.5 sq km and reaches a maximum altitude of about 150 meters on the surrounding sandy plain. Along its western half part, a spectacular terrace develops at the base of a sandstone bed carved into a sequence of shelters (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Panorama of the Sivré hill from the SW (Photo Mauro Colella). Three massive sandstone beds of Cambrian age outcrop along its western side. All the Sivré painted shelters open at the base of the second sandstone bed, except Sivré III and Sivré III-P1.

Figure 3. Sixteen looted tumuli on a low rocky spur, at the south-western tip of the Sivré hill.

Near the south-western tip of the hill, in coincidence with the western side of the Sivré II shelter, this terrace narrows until it becomes impassable. To avoid the obstacle, it is necessary to go up and down along easy ramps leading to a low rocky spur covered by small tumuli (Fig. 3).

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Figure 4. Sivré IV shelter (top: the original RGB image – bottom: processed by *DStretch_CRGB*). Elephant outline drawn in dark red, characterized by butterfly-shaped ears and upward curving tusks. A small human with stocky arms and sturdy legs posed as advancing faces the animal. An unidentified rounded shape and a crescent shape overlap the elephant's body.

Grard Bailloud (†2010) first visited the Sivr shelters in 1957, during the “Mission des Confins du Tchad”, organised by the Muse de l’Homme (Paris). Looking for rock art, he discovered a set of paintings not directly associated with depictions of domesticated animals. These paintings, attributed to the Archaic Period (Bailloud 1960), i.e. to the pre-pastoral period in Saharan terms, are present in a variety of contrasting styles and execution techniques, implying a considerable time-depth.

The Bailloud’s approach to the Ennedi rock art was very selective since he surveyed by direct tracing on transparent sheets, a time-consuming procedure, shooting medium format B&W photography only in the most favourable conditions. Thus, the five published human figures attributed to the Sivr style by this pioneering archaeologist were just a sample of the art studied in the field.

Bailloud (1997) wrote that *“The outcroppings at Sivr IV (27 km WSW of Fada) conserve numerous vestiges of the archaic period as well as paintings from the final bovine and dromedary periods. The archaic period paintings are, however, in poor condition. The Sivr and Elikeo styles are well represented here, with more recent superimposed figures of a white checked pattern. We were only able to trace one large red linear elephant from the ceiling; this animal is awkward, with butterfly-shaped ears and rounded feet.”*

Worth to note, Bailloud (1997) used in its relative chronology the term “Bovine”, which is presently a deprecated term (Di Lernia 2017). Thus, the term “Cattle” is the preferred synonym here adopted for designating the Middle, Recent and Final “Bovine” periods.

Bailloud reported from Sivr IV only the mentioned painted elephant (Fig. 4). He did not publish any of the poorly preserved paintings in the Checked style present in Sivr I ([Model 23](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017a) nor the faint paintings of the Archaic Period found in Sivr II, including some idiosyncratic motifs (Fig. 5 to 9; [Model 19](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017a). In fact, the importance of these paintings for confirming the regional chronology at the local level can be appreciated only by modern digital technologies. With no surprise, Bailloud also disregarded the abundant pastoral art of the Recent Cattle, Final Cattle and Camel periods present at various locations in Sivr, in all hundreds of paintings, since he already surveyed elsewhere much more significant examples. This late art is located aside the paintings of the Archaic or Middle Cattle periods as observed in the cases of Sivr I-P1, Sivr III-P1 ([Model 20](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017a) and Sivr IV-P1. For some reasons, the late artists avoided painting over pre-existent art.

While the Sivr paintings are easy to find and represent a touristic attraction, the whereabouts of the Sivr IV paintings others than the elephant were previously unknown since Bailloud did not give a hint at their actual location. The relocation of these lost paintings eventually occurred in February 2017 thanks to the efforts of a small party of devoted Saharan travellers. The relief of these paintings was carried out by close-range photogrammetry. The orthographic projections of the [3D models](#) developed with Photoscan (Agisoft LLC, St. Petersburg, Russia) and MeshLab (Cignoni et al. 2008) represent accurate maps of the decorated surfaces, not affected by scale variations related to the photographic perspective. Since the ancient paintings are weathered and in most cases not visible to the naked eye, all the digital images acquired have been systematically enhanced with the DStretch software (Harman 2017, Le Quellec et al. 2013).

Figure 5. Sivré II shelter (top: the original RGB image – bottom: processed by *DStretch_LDS*). A crouched human framed in a shallow oval niche, an elephant, a possible masculine sex symbol, and a figure vaguely resembling a fish. This last one is better identifiable with an anthropomorphic figure since the right “fin” has strokes recalling the usual way of depicting toes in the Sivré style. The small, solid-coloured human figures shown in various dynamic poses compare positively to the figures attributed to the Mayguili style, the oldest in the regional chronology established by Bailloud (1997).

The digital images of the famed Sivré panels published as hand-drawings by Bailloud (1997), necessary for the comparison with the Sivré IV unreported paintings, are available as 3D models on the Sketchfab portal (Menardi Noguera 2017a). These models offer a photographic resolution unattainable by standard publishing formats, documenting at the same time the topography of the decorated surfaces, which is critical for understanding the art since the medium always constrains the artist's choices.

The vast collection of pictures acquired by the Thrust of African Rock Art (TARA), published online by the British Museum, constituted an excellent additional resource for the comparative analysis of the previously unreported rock art.

The Chadian Ministry of Tourism granted the permit to travel to the Ennedi and visiting the rock art sites. The photographic documentation of the Sivré paintings here presented was acquired without interfering in any way with the art, without touching or disturbing any visible archaeological remains, in full respect of the Chart by the Amis de l'Art Rupestre Saharienne (AARS 2009).

2. The Sivré style

The paintings in the peculiar style named after Sivré are rare in the set of 500 painted sites visited during the 1956 mission (Bailloud 1997). For a long time, these particular paintings appeared as an oddity in the regional frame of the Ennedi rock art (Scarpa Falce & Scarpa Falce 1996). Nowadays, thanks to a surge of travelling parties and the generalised adoption of digital technology in documenting rock art, the number of sites decorated with paintings attributable to this style is steadily growing (Menardi Noguera 2014a, 2014b and 2017b). Nevertheless, the published sample is not statistically significant for a morphometric revision of the original style definition proposed as preliminary by Bailloud (1997). Taking into account the most recent findings and constraining the description to the anthropomorphic figures only, the features of the Sivré style summarise as follows:

- A discoid shape represents the head, generally shown in smaller proportions than in the western canon exemplified by the Vitruvian Man. Anatomic facial details are missing. The torso appears disproportionately long. Arms are sometimes shorter than natural or reduced to stumps. The lower limbs have an oversized appearance. Blunt terminations depict the hands and feet; single traits represent the fingers and toes. Gendering by the depiction of primary sex attributes, i.e. the penis for men and bosoms as protuberances on the thorax side in women (Menardi Noguera 2015a, 2017a and [Model 21](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017b), is sometimes in use. Inverted triangularly shaped thorax and muscular legs may indicate the physical structure of sturdy men (Menardi Noguera 2015a).
- Anthropomorphic figures drawn by the outline with a solid white infill, resembling the phantom caricature of cartoonists, are present in Sivré I and Sivré II (Fig. 7). Similar figures are also visible in the Elikeo III shelter (Fig. 3 in Choppy & Scarpa Falce 1997). The stylization of the head as a rounded tapering termination of the body, the simple postural representation in the A-pose, i.e. the standing pose with dangling arms, the missing articulations and fingers, make these specific figures not directly comparable to the human

Figure 6. Sivré II shelter, northern sector (processed by *DStretch_LDS*). Detail of the crouched human framed in a shallow oval niche. The toes depicted as short segments, the dots and stripes decorating the legs are distinctive of the Sivré style. This crouched human overlaps small solid-coloured anthropomorphic figures, relatively fainter.

Figure 7. Sivré II shelter (left: the original RGB image – right: processed by *DStretch_YRD*). An isolated standing human figure painted with a red outline and white fill. The head, shaped like a tapered, rounded end of the upper body, has no discernible neck.

depictions attributed to the Sivré style by Bailloud (1997). Instead, these paintings could depict anthropomorphic beings of unknown nature, still related to the Sivré style, or could represent an unrelated group of paintings.

Figure 8. Sivré II shelter (processed by *DStretch_YBK*). Stencil hand with six fingers and a double halo, likely produced by a second impression.

Figure 9. Sivré II shelter (processed by *DStretch_CRGB*). A stencil hand and a small human figure in solid red. The knuckle width is eight cm only.

- The iconographic elements of the human figure include body decorations in the form of dots and stripes (Menardi Noguera 2017a, and [Model 16](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017b). Dots, likely representing tattooing or body paintings, more evident on the legs but at times extended to the whole body including the face, are common to men and women. Stripes decorate the limbs and crossed stripes decorate the trunk ([Model 22](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017b). Bows and arrows are the men's paraphernalia (Fig. 4 and 5 in Menardi Noguera 2014a).
- Drawing by outlines, typically in a dark hue of red, is the most frequent technique featuring the known Sivré paintings. A solid infill in a light whitish paint of unknown nature is sometimes visible. However, this predominance could be partly due to a taphonomic effect. Survival of paintings according to the employed technique is indicated by the elephants

decorating the Gherbescina shelter (Fig. 3, 4, 11 and 12 in Menardi Noguera 2015b), all comparable by stylization conventions to the Sivré IV elephant (Fig. 4). The Gherbescina elephants painted in solid red are invisible to the naked eye while the very remarkable elephants painted in white are well-evident, but lacking any detectable red outline.

The two outstanding crouched human figures discovered by Bailloud (1960) on the ceiling of the Sivré III shelter (Menardi Noguera 2017a) justifies the choice of the Sivré label for naming this pre-pastoral style. Bailloud dubbed these figures the “Deux Martiens” referring to the humorous nickname adopted by Henri Lhote (1958) for the Round Heads paintings of the Tassili (Algeria). Seventy years after their discovery, this suggestive couple is still unparalleled among the known paintings of the Archaic Period for their artistic quality.

Up to recent times, the best documentation available of the “Two Martians” corresponded to the well-executed hand drawing by Bailloud (1960) since film pictures by later researchers failed to reproduce the same resolution and density of details (Fig. 2, Pl. A and Pl. M in Scarpa Falce & Scarpa Falce 1996). Fortunately, modern digital images from Sivré III ([Model 16](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017a) show that the dotted body decorations, organised in festoons over the legs, extend to the whole body up to the faces. Bands decorate the body from the lower limbs to the neck, while short stripes hang from the arms and shoulders. These last details, interpreted as shoulder plumages (Bailloud 1960), more likely represent the loose ends of bands of fabric tightly wrapped around the body and limbs. In fact, the flesh of the legs around these decorations looks realistically swelled. This couple is evidently busy in some social activity. The figure to the right is emphatically gesturing holding with the right hand a sort of crescent-shaped suspended coup and brandishing with the upraised left hand a small object resembling a mug.

In addition to a complete view of the body decorations characterising the “Two Martians”, digital images reveal the protuberance of one bosom below the armpit of the right arm of the right figure allowing identification with a woman (Menardi Noguera 2017a). Very likely, the “Martian” couple, formerly considered composed of men (Bailloud 1960), represents two women since, by body proportions, the left figure is similar to the right figure.

3. Sivré IV, the elephant with butterfly-shaped ears

Butterfly-shaped ears and feet in twisted perspective characterise the Sivré IV elephant (Fig. 4) described as “awkward” for its unnatural body proportions (Bailloud 1997). Stylization features of this famed painting mirror a common tradition in the Ennedi as proven by the painted elephants discovered in the Gherbescina shelter (Fig. 4 and 12 in Menardi Noguera 2014), and also by the well-known engraved and polished elephant on the eastern side of the Chiguéou natural arch (Menardi Noguera 2016).

Animal depictions with feet shown in a twisted perspective are recurrent in unrelated rock art from faraway countries, a fact easy to explain by a common perceptive process (Deręgowski 2005). Instead, butterfly-shaped ears in elephants seem more indicative of a genuine artistic tradition extending from

the western Tibesti to the river Nile in Upper Egypt (Fig. 4 and 7 in Huard & Allard 1977).

A grossly retracing in white put in evidence the dark outline of the elephant body. Since Bailloud (1997) did not mention any secondary white contour, this additional detail looks more likely the work of an indelicate modern visitor rather than the result of an ancient repainting act. Worth to mention, this white retracing is visible in the first published picture of the elephant, shot in 2013 by David Coulson (British Museum online collections, Number: [2013.2034.6705](#)).

The enhanced images of the Sivré IV panel reveal the existence to the left of the elephant of a small human figure drawn by the outline (Fig. 5). This human looks posed as advancing towards the pachyderm. A globular dotted shape and an unidentified crescent shape painted in red overlap the elephant body. The crescent shape has two slim appendices resembling cloven-hoofed legs.

The vestiges of the Archaic Period mentioned by Bailloud (1997) are evidently not present inside the shelter hosting the elephant, nor they appear in the extension of the shelter to the north, nor in its north-eastern dependencies, richly decorated with paintings of the recent pastoral and Ancient Camel periods. A stepped passage to the left of the elephant shelter, partially hidden by a tall block, leads to the southern prosecution of the Sivré IV ledge, where two modest shelters open (Fig. 1). These two shelters, here named Sivré IV-A and Sivré IV-B, host the paintings pointed out by Bailloud.

4. Sivré IV-A

The Sivré IV-A shelter opens to the south-west and is sunlit most of the day (Fig. 10). The back wall bears traces of unrecoverable paintings in the form of tiny red dots visible on enhanced images only. Partially decipherable paintings survive on the inner portion of the ceiling, which escaped weathering by percolating waters and demolition by exfoliation (Fig. 11).

Digital enhancement of the left ceiling segment reveals the existence of an ancient weathering border, double-crossing the panel as a festoon at 1.5 m from the western corner of the shelter. The faint relic of a motif constituted by a grid of thick angled lines filled with dots, seemingly finger-painted, decorate the surface to the left of this festoon (Fig. 12).

Worth to mention, DStretch processed images show the existence of an unreported finger-painted motif also in the well-known site of Sivré I (Fig. 13; [Model 21](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017b).

Fragments of paintings drawn by thin red outlines, internally decorated with grids of angled lines, densely fill the surface of a triangularly shaped gap opened by exfoliation (Fig. 14). The legs of a human drawn by the outline occupy the centre. To their right, a much confused dark shape with ten appendices is present (Fig. 15). Its upper part looks like a positive handprint, with the thumb pointing to the left. Curved appendices, perhaps produced by smearing paint with the fingers, jut out from the lower part of this motif.

Bailloud (1997, Fig. 26 and 27) described two painted hands in the Helikeo III shelter, one drawn by outline and the second in solid red as the unique occurrences of this type he was able to document in 500 visited rock art sites. However, this kind of motif could be less rare than these data suggest since it is easy to miss handprints while looking for figurative art (Smith 2017). In particular, stencil hands might resemble natural stains of the rock as the stippled haloes have no sharp external borders. The two

Figure 10. The Sivré IV-A shelter as viewed from the south-west.

Figure 11. Sivré IV-A shelter, orthophoto of the ceiling with locator boxes for the images discussed in the text.

stencil hands visible in the Sivré II shelter (Fig. 8 and 9) escaped detection by Bailloud. They are part of a context devoid of pastoral art, consisting of a very heterogeneous assemblage of figures painted by red outlines and small humans painted in solid red. These figures are respectively attributable to the Sivré and the Mayguili styles on a comparative basis with the published art (Fig. 30 and 31 in Bailloud 1997).

Figure 12. Sivré IV-A shelter, location A1 (processed by *DStretch_CRGB*). Fragmentary painted motif composed by a grid of thick angled lines filled with dots, seemingly finger-painted. This relic decorates a triangularly shaped segment of the ceiling bounded by an ancient weathering border.

Figure 13. Sivré I shelter, western section of the back wall (processed by *DStretch_YRD*). Rounded shape enclosing a motif constituted by a thick wavy line flanked by dots, and two round shapes. The indented lower one encircles an anthropomorphic or animal figure drawn by the outline, laying horizontally.

Figure 14. Sivré IV-A shelter, location A2 (processed by *DStretch_CRGB*). Fragmentary painted patterns drawn by thin red outlines, internally decorated with cross-line patterns. This relic fills a triangular-shaped segment of the ceiling bounded by an old weathering border. In the dense group of indecipherable paintings, the legs of a human drawn by the outline stand out in the centre.

In the lack of superimposition relations with the other visible paintings on the panel, it is not possible to guess a relative age for the hand motifs.

In the right sector of the Sivré IV-A ceiling, enhanced images evidence eight fragmentary human figures drawn by the contour lines (Fig. 16; [Model 24](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017b). Stumpy arms and rounded heads are indicative of paintings in the Sivré style. The crossed stripes decorating the chest of one of the human figure shown in the panel are also diagnostic of the style (Fig. 17) as well as the tiny fragment of a reticular motif reminiscent of a wickerwork object. This one recalls the reticular motif depicted at the feet of the partially preserved figure decorating the eastern sector of Sivré I surveyed by Bailloud (1997, Fig. 35), perhaps representing a basket or traps ([Model 22](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017b). To the upper right of this poorly preserved composition, a fragmentary human figure stands out for the dark hue of its outline and the internal decorative pattern of angled and dotted lines extending to the head (Fig. 17). This particular decorated fragmentary figure is comparable for the filling pattern made of lines and points with the figures from the Elikeo III shelter representing the reference paintings for the Elikeo style (Fig. 44 in Bailloud 1997).

Figure 15. Sivré IV-A shelter, location A3 (processed by *DStretch_LDS*). A dark shape with appendages. Its upper part resembles a positive handprint, with the thumb pointing to the right.

Figure 16. Sivré IV-A shelter, location A4 (processed by *DStretch_CRGB* plus digital retracing). Eight fragmentary human figures drawn by the contour line, without discernible body infill, form a complex composition.

Figure 17. Sivré IV-A shelter, detail from location A4 (processed by *DStretch_CRGB*). Fragmentary human figure. Patterns of angled and dotted lines decorate the head and body. On the lower-left corner a human figure with stumpy arms, short hairs and crisscrossed stripes wrapping the trunk.

5. Sivré IV-B

The Sivré IV-B shelter (Fig. 18) preserves painting only on the ceiling, a flat surface crossed diagonally by a stepping discontinuity (Fig. 19). At the centre of the left sector, a well-preserved running figure painted in white is present (Fig. 20). Body proportions look realistic and convey the impression of a slim constitution. Patterns of thin angled lines fill the body of this figure drawn by the outline. These lines form a dense grid on the torso, enriched by thicker longitudinal lines more densely traced on the left side, which exalts the dynamically posed body. It is a sophisticated painting technique requiring a thin paintbrush and a skilled hand, astonishingly similar to the modern crosshatching technique employed by etchers to render the three-dimensionality of the subjects. Four white bands traverse horizontally the upper head giving a squared appearance to the front. Facial details are missing.

A checked vertical appendix, with a rounded top, decorates the nape. This appendix likely represents a feather. Rounded triangularly shaped protuberances, filled with a pattern of angled lines, shown above the shoulders, could depict a body decoration made of plumage. The rounded object hanging below the left armpit could represent a small bag. Three parallel segments extending across the left hand very likely depict a clutch of arrows. A long, vertical line extending vertically across the right hand probably

Figure 18. The Sivré IV-B shelter viewed from east.

represents a bow. This finely drawn white runner superimposes fragmentary paintings drawn with a dark outline contour (Fig. 20), here interpreted as the paired legs of two human figures, much larger than the white running archer. Ten single strokes represent the toes of the rightmost figure, a distinctive stylisation convention typical of the Sivré style. Percolating water destroyed the upper bodies of these two ancient figures, painted in the sector of the panel more proximal to the shelter exterior.

To the left of the white runner, the legs of a third standing human figure, drawn by a white outline without a recognisable infill, is present (Fig. 20). The incumbent weathering border obliterated the upper body of this elongated figure, which feet point to the left as the two previously mentioned relics of humans.

In the right sector of the ceiling toward the shelter brow, the relics of three human figures drawn by white outlines in different dimensions stand out (Fig. 21). Patterns of crossed thin angled lines fill their bodies. The poses of the two best-preserved ones and the scanty remains of the others suggest a group scene composed of people running towards the left, being the imaginary baseline parallel to the shelter back wall. An oval head characterises the figure most significant by its dimensions, apparently placed in the foreground. His tapered nape ends in a white dot, topped by a long appendix, possibly representing a feather with barbs. This figure holds with the left hand one long object drawn as a double closed line, perhaps representing a bow.

Figure 19. Sivré IV-B, orthophoto of the shelter ceiling with locator boxes for the images discussed in the text. The zenith of the conventional vertical direction orienting the human figures painted on the flat horizontal surface is towards the exterior of the shelter. Prehistoric painters created their art facing the back wall of the shelter.

The head of the second, best-preserved runner depicted on the upper right is missing. A rounded object, likely a small bag, hangs below the left forearm. Relics of two human figures preserved only by the torso, tights and forearms, follow to the right of these runners (Fig. 22). The first one is a figure painted in red, filled with a checked decoration. High-resolution images of the rightmost one, painted in solid white, evidence a dense pattern or longitudinal paintbrush strokes filling the legs. Enhanced images show the waist and tights of this human overlap a much-smaller standing figure shown in a frontal pose, painted in red, internally decorated with dotted and angled lines (Fig. 23).

In the lower right sector of the ceiling, near the back wall of the shelter, an oval pattern painted in red outlines, with appendages resembling human arms with open hands, superimposes a human figure painted in solid white (Fig. 24). A second human figure painted in solid white is present nearby, further to the right. The imaginary baseline of these two humans is perpendicular to the back wall of the shelter, an orientation inconsistent with the runners in the Checked style. In the middle-right sector of the ceiling, a third human figure and a poorly defined quadruped painted in solid white are shown in the same orientation (Fig. 25). The two pointed protrusions on the muzzle of this animal suggest a rhino identification.

Figure 20. Sivré IV-B shelter, location B1 (processed by *DStretch_LDS*). A running figure of a slim constitution. Patterns of thin cross-lines fill the body and the feather worn in the hairstyle. This figure overlaps the legs of two paired elongated figures with no preserved upper bodies.

Figure 21. Sivré IV-B shelter, location B2 (processed by *DStretch_LDS*). Faded human figures drawn by white outlines, filled with thin cross-lines. A long appendage, presumably representing a feather with barbs, surmounts the tapering nape of the largest figure in the group.

Figure 22. Sivré IV-B shelter, location B3 (processed by *DStretch_LDS*). Relics of two figures filled with checked patterns, preserved only by the torso, tights and forearms.

6. Conclusions

Most of the previously unreported paintings of the Archaic Period present in Sivré are in a fragmentary state. However, superimposition relations among these paintings document the relative chronology of the Archaic Period at the intra-site level. These superimpositions are consistent with the regional chronology of the Archaic Period proposed as preliminary by Bailloud (1997), based on an extensive set of sites. In particular, the relocation of the “lost” archaic paintings of Sivré IV and the newly acquired high-resolution 3D photographic models of the known panels in Sivré offer good evidence about the superimposition relations between the figures in the Checked style with the paintings in the Sivré style, which result older (Fig. 25).

The human figures in the Checked style present in Sivré are straightforwardly comparable to the reference figures documented in the Elikeo III shelter by Bailloud (1997). As observed in Sivré IV-B, the superimposition relation between motifs attributable to the Checked style and the Elikeo style indicates that these last ones are relatively older (Fig. 28). Noteworthy, Bailloud himself stressed the close similarity existent between these two styles. Since this familiarity could imply that one style is merely a variant of the other, the need of more observations at the regional level to confirm the regularity and chronological meaning of the superimposition documented in Sivré VI-B is evident.

The reassessment of the relative chronology of the Ennedi rock art of the Archaic Period also benefits

Figure 23. Sivré IV-B shelter, detail from location B3 (processed by *DStretch_LDS*). The waist and tights of the white relic figure overlap a smaller standing human figure in frontal view, painted in red, internally decorated with dotted and angled lines.

Figure 24. Sivré IV-B shelter, location B4 (processed by *DStretch_LDS*). An oval motif painted by red outlines, with strange articulated appendix resembling human arms with open hands, superimposes a human figure painted in solid white.

Figure 25. Sivré IV-B shelter, location B5 (processed by *DStretch_LDS*). A quadruped and a human figure painted in solid white. The head shape of the animal looks poorly defined. The two pointed protuberances could represent the horns of a rhino. The picture is rotated 90 degrees counter-clockwise; the shelter exterior is to the left.

from the idiosyncratic paintings of Sivré II since the human figure best adherent to the distinctive characteristics of the Sivré style (Fig. 6) overlaps anthropomorphic figures in solid colour. Bailloud (1997) attributes to the Mayguili style small figures in solid red, posed as dancing, often associated by proximity with paintings in the Sivré style. This association, also seen in Archeï-2 (Menardi Noguera 2014), suggests the heralds of the Sivré style felt attraction for the same surfaces initially chosen by the first comers who painted the small red figures. This deduction is not trivial since many Ennedi shelters are gigantic and there was more than enough virgin space available as a canvas for the early artists of the Archaic Period. Confusing superimpositions were easily avoidable at the dawn of artistic creation in the Ennedi. The choices made by the late pastoral painters in Sivré demonstrate that there was no need to reuse the same panels for initiating a new artistic cycle, whatever were the religious or social motivations to frequent and paint the same shelters.

It is necessary to outline that a single superimposition case is not enough to establish a relative chronology. Some motifs could express variants of a unique style and superimpositions might be theoretically casual and without real chronologic value. Caution should always apply since apparent inversion of superimposition relations can occur with paints characterised by different physical properties. A porous surface already saturated with paint can repel a new pictorial layer or favour the washing of the secondly applied paint. Such possibility does not seem the case of the discussed superimpositions, where the lower layer emerges through the upper layer in transparency or the overlap is on fainter motifs.

Acknowledgements

Acknowledgments: Paolo Carmignoto, Mauro Colella, Pascale Hégy, and Nicole Honoré kindly assisted the photographic acquisition of the Sivré Paintings. Spazi d'Avventura, specialised tour operator based in Milan, in the person of Tommaso Ravà, provided with much kindness the logistics. The Société des Voyages Sahariens -Tchad, a renewed Chadian travelling organisation, provided the official permit to travel to the Ennedi and visiting the rock art sites.

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The lost archaic paintings of Sivré IV (Ennedi, Chad)

Sivré I, shelter ceiling (left: the original RGB image – right: processed by *DStretch_LDS*). A running figure partially filled with a pattern of angled and cross-lines. An appendix inserted on the nape at an angle, likely representing a single feather with barbs. This slim runner is holding a square object. To the lower left of the runner, a small solid-coloured human figure is present ([Model 23](#) in Menardi Noguera 2017a).